

Research Article

21st Century Skills and Inclusive Education: A Case in Limpiado Memorial Foundation-Lightbringer Learning Center

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ABSTRACT

This study generally aims to find out the 21st century skills practiced by teachers and students the knowledge and skills in inclusive education of teachers and students in private schools in Biliran. Mix-method research design were utilized in this study involving collection, analysis and integration of quantity and qualitative data that uses survey questionnaires and several questions for feedbacks. Knowledge and skills of teachers had already been performed and agreed in both regular education teachers and special education teachers. Students have knowledge and skills in inclusive education. Students' respondents can adjust and acknowledge the different needs of classmates inside the classroom. Learning and innovation and information, media and technology knowledge and skills practiced by teachers are significantly related. However, life and career skills are not directly affected by knowledge and skills practiced by teachers. Further, learning and innovation skills are not directly related or affected by student's knowledge and skills in inclusive education while information, media and technology and life and career are significantly related to student's knowledge and skills. Lastly, understanding in inclusive education anchors in learners with special needs, inclusive education and learning, and equality in education. There's a feeling happiness, satisfaction, and understanding felt by teachers inside inclusive classroom. Teachers possesses communication skills, analytical teaching skills and social and understanding skills in handling inclusive class. Leadership training, social responsibility, and team building are trainings that helps improve and increase teachers motivation and commitment in teaching inclusive education class were the aim is to give quality education for all.

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1. Introduction

Twenty first century skills practices comprise skills, abilities and learning dispositions that have been identified as being required for success in 21st century society and workplaces by educators. Many of these skills and practices are associated with learning and innovation skills, information, media and technology skills, life and career skills (E. Heretape, 2018).

The basic idea is that students, who will come of age in the 21st century, need to be taught different skills than those learned by students in the 20th century, and that the skills they learn should reflect the specific demands that will be placed upon them in a complex, competitive, knowledge-based, information-age, technology-driven economy and society (www.edglossary.org, 2018).

Asia Society report, Saavedra and Opfer (2012), summarized lessons from research on learning to identify promising strategies for teaching 21st century competencies. For example, they stressed the importance of making curriculum relevant, helping students learn how to teach themselves, and fostering creativity. This report builds on that foundation by examining how to assess 21st century competencies. Fortunately, data systems and measurement techniques that provide opportunities to assess students' attainment of these outcomes are increasingly available. This report is intended to acquaint teachers, school leaders, and district administrators with the current state of 21st century competencies assessment, provide examples of relevant measures that educators in the field may wish to consider using, and offer some guidance to help educators compare measures and implement an assessment system.

On the other hand, inclusive education is when all students, regardless of any challenges they may have, are placed in age-appropriate general education classes that are in their own neighborhood school to receive high-quality instruction, interventions, and supports that enable them to meet success in the core curriculum. It is very important so that children are able to part of their community and develop a sense of

belonging and become better prepared for life in the community as children and adults and provide better opportunities for learning. (Murphy, 2014), emphasized that teachers have a unique privilege of spending months at a time getting to know the learners who make up their classes, with all their abilities, talents, strengths and needs. One of the joys of teaching career has been to witness the way the fabric of the class dynamic is woven from the range of abilities of the learners. It has been an experience that the diversity of the learners' abilities regardless of who they are bring richness to their relationships with each other and with their teacher, making each class unique and interesting in its own way (Chaula, 2014).

A comprehensive review of the literature (de Boer, Pijl, & Minnaert, 2015) found that on average, parents are somewhat uncertain if inclusion is a good option for their students with disabilities (SWD). On the upside, the more experience with inclusive education they had, the more positive parents of SWD were about it. Additionally, parents of regular students held a decidedly positive attitude toward inclusive education.

The school and classroom operate on the premise that students with disabilities are as fundamentally competent as students without disabilities. Therefore, all students can be full participants in their classrooms and in the local school community. Much of the movement is related to legislation that students receive their education in the least restrictive environment (LRE). This means they are with their peers without disabilities to the maximum degree possible, with general education the placement of first choice for all students (Alquraini & Gut, 2012). Similarly, Cook (2011) revealed that teacher attitudes about inclusion in their classrooms stemmed from their lack of confidence and perceived lack of proper training in that area.

The future is very bright indeed for this approach. The evidence is mounting that inclusive education and classrooms are able to not only meet the requirements of least restrictive environment for students with disabilities, but to benefit regular education students as well. We see that with exposure both parents and teachers become more positive. Training and support

allow regular education teachers to implement inclusive education with ease and success. All around it's a win-win!

It is in this study that, 21st century skills practices and inclusive education will put together and enhance development not only for regular students but also for students with disabilities and letting them experience the real 21st classroom scenario.

2. Methods

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-sequential research design by Creswell, 2005 in obtaining data wherein the researcher assessed the 21st century skills practices and inclusive education knowledge and skills of teachers and students of Light-bringer Learning Center.

Research Respondents

The research respondents of this study are the teachers and students of Limpiado Memorial Foundation Incorporate. The target number of respondents will be drawn from the teachers and students populations.
Research Instruments.

The instrument that will be utilize in the study will be adapted from descriptive questionnaire survey for

the Teachers' Practices on the 21st Century Skills published paper. Standardize survey questionnaires develop by Eric Heretape, Faculty of the Department of Education Bukidnon State University. Part II, on qualitative design for inclusive education developed by Blackie Cara on her paper The Perception of Educators Towards Inclusive Education in a Sample of Government School.

Data Gathering Procedure and Data Scoring

The researcher will wrote a formal request to all the teachers and students of the Limpiado Memorial Foundation Incorporated for the dissemination and distribution of the questionnaires. The questionnaires will be personally given to the respondents of the study. The conduct of the interview will done one on one with the researcher using interview guide for inclusive education.

All the data collected from the respondents were systematically tabulated, tallied, analyzed, carefully described, and interpreted in order to attain the accurate information needed.

The data were categorized according to the variables of the study. To determine the 21st century skills practices of the teachers and students. The following data scoring will be utilize:

Table 1
21st Century Skills Practiced by the Teachers in terms of Learning Innovation

Learning and Innovation	WM	Description
1. Brainstorm and seek out opportunities for learners to improve their ideas and on the way they react to situations.	4.2	Often
2. Manipulate models and simulations for the learners to experiment and create new ideas.	3.7	Often
3. Make graphic organizers to illustrate difficult topics.	3.7	Often
4. Provide learners with performance standards by which their work will be evaluated.	4.4	Always
5. Observe the learners while they are having the self-learning in the classroom.	4.8	Always
6. Ensure that a more comprehensive approach to inquiry that includes wonder and reflection must be used in the classroom.	4.3	Always
7. Use engaging instruction strategies suitable to instructional purposes and learners' levels and learning styles.	4.1	Often
8. Guide the learners in examining reliability, bias, or credibility of claims by means of giving activities that suit in.	4.3	Always
9. Facilitate the learners in organizing, classifying, questioning or evaluating the work of their classmates.	4.6	Always
10. Consider context or incorporate different perspectives to evaluate thoughts or actions.	4.0	Often
11. Bring together relevant information and perspectives to inform thoughts, actions or belief of learners.	4.4	Always
12. Synthesize and interpret information by asking essential questions that help clarify a path towards better solutions.	4.3	Always
13. Break problems into smaller or simpler parts and develop criteria in solving problems.	4.2	Often
14. Select problems that are applicable to real life situations and set the learners to find solution.	4.3	Always
15. Prepare some worksheet for the learners to complete after watching the video.	3.7	Often
16. Respect the experience or views of my learners and others when expressing options or ideas without bias.	4.5	Always
17. Support or empower learners and co-teachers who are reluctant to share their knowledge or views.	4.5	Always
18. Create collaborative groups activities to encourage participation and shared leadership.	4.2	Often
19. Allow an open conference style of interaction rather than the one-way seating of traditional desk.	4.1	Often
20. Focus on project-based learning which enables learners to put knowledge together in the form of focused questions and assessments for the project.	3.9	Often
AWM	4.2	Often

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered in this study were tallied, processed into frequency counts, analyzed and interpreted using the appropriate statistical tools namely: frequency, percentage, mean, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. On the qualitative design of the inclusive education sequential, explanatory and thematic design will be utilize.

Results and Discussion

21st Century Skills Practiced by the Teachers
Table 1 presents the 21st century skills practiced by the teachers.

Learning innovation

Table 2
21st Century Skills Practiced by the Teachers in terms of Information, Media and Technology

Information, Media and Technology	WM	Description
1. Participate in accessing information in an effective manner which is related to the learners learning.	4.3	Always
2. Find resources such as databases, documentary films and websites to be utilized in class as sources of information.	3.5	Often
3. Help the learners appreciate literature and other creative expressions of information.	4.1	Often
4. Encourage collaborative learning in order to participate effectively and generate valuable information.	4.2	Often
5. Evaluate the resources and the available information.	4.0	Often
6. Provide opportunities for learners to gather information online.	3.7	Often
7. Offer a variety of ways for learners to repackaging information and authentic media learning experience.	3.7	Often
8. Help the learners recognize the false information in all forms of media.	4.0	Often
9. Incorporate and integrate different forms of media into instruction.	3.6	Often
10. Use ICT in creating materials for learners' use.	3.5	Often
11. Use PowerPoint presentation with moving clip art or animation for them to feel and catch the attention of the pupils.	3.5	Often
12. Access internet resources for planning instruction or collecting ideas.	4.0	Often
13. Communicate to colleagues by means of social media.	3.8	Often
14. Make internet as a tool for giving learners assessments and assignment.	3.8	Often
15. Educate learners on how to use computers for learning.	3.4	Sometimes
16. Utilize the e-class record in determining learners' achievement.	4.0	Often
17. Submit computer-generated reports.	4.2	Often
18. Update myself on educational trends and issues through internet access.	4.2	Often
19. Make printed materials in remediation for slow learners.	4.2	Often
20. Use interactive technology for learning such as school purchased instructional software.	3.8	Often
AWM	3.9	Often

As shown in table 1, under learning innovations on the 21st century skills practiced by the teachers. There are twenty indicators in learning and innovation and "Observe the learners while they are having the self-learning in the classroom" had the highest weighted mean of 4.8 as "Always" followed by "Facilitate the learners in organizing, classifying, questioning or evaluating the work of their classmates" 4.6 weighted mean as "Always". "Respect the experience or views of my learners and others when expressing options or ideas without bias." and "Support or empower learners and co-teachers who are reluctant to share their knowledge or views." with weighted mean of 4.5 respectively as "Always". "Provide learners with performance standards by which their work will be evaluated." with a weighted

mean of 4.4 as "Always" and so on and so forth. It has an overall weighted mean of 4.2 described as "often" which implies that teachers are often practiced the 21st century skills in their teaching. In summing up, there are ten indicators, answered by research respondents as "Always" practiced the 21st century skills under learning innovations. On the other hand, there are also ten indicators answered by research respondents as "Often". Further, 21st century skills under learning innovation had always and often practiced by teachers' respondents. This further implies that, students had acquire learning innovation skills through their teachers as they are practicing the 21st century skills.

Information, media and technology

Table 2
21st Century Skills Practiced by the Teachers in terms of Information, Media and Technology

Information, Media and Technology	WM	Description
21. Participate in accessing information in an effective manner which is related to the learners learning.	4.3	Always
22. Find resources such as databases, documentary films and websites to be utilized in class as sources of information.	3.5	Often
23. Help the learners appreciate literature and other creative expressions of information.	4.1	Often
24. Encourage collaborative learning in order to participate effectively and generate valuable information.	4.2	Often
25. Evaluate the resources and the available information.	4.0	Often
26. Provide opportunities for learners to gather information online.	3.7	Often
27. Offer a variety of ways for learners to repackage information and authentic media learning experience.	3.7	Often
28. Help the learners recognize the false information in all forms of media.	4.0	Often
29. Incorporate and integrate different forms of media into instruction.	3.6	Often
30. Use ICT in creating materials for learners' use.	3.5	Often
31. Use PowerPoint presentation with moving clip art or animation for them to feel and catch the attention of the pupils.	3.5	Often
32. Access internet resources for planning instruction or collecting ideas.	4.0	Often
33. Communicate to colleagues by means of social media.	3.8	Often
34. Make internet as a tool for giving learners assessments and assignment.	3.8	Often
35. Educate learners on how to use computers for learning.	3.4	Sometimes
36. Utilize the e-class record in determining learners' achievement.	4.0	Often
37. Submit computer-generated reports.	4.2	Often
38. Update myself on educational trends and issues through internet access.	4.2	Often
39. Make printed materials in remediation for slow learners.	4.2	Often
40. Use interactive technology for learning such as school purchased instructional software.	3.8	Often
AWM	3.9	Often

As reflected in table 2, of the twenty indicators, "Participate in accessing information in an effective manner which is related to the learners' learning." got a weighted mean of 4.3 which described as "Always." "Educate learners on how to use computers for learning." got a weighted mean of 3.4 which described as "Sometimes". While the rest of the eighteen indicators got a weighted mean under "Often". It implies that research respondents are participating in

accessing effective manner related to learning but sometimes they are educating their learners on how to use computer for learning. It has an overall weighted mean of 3.9 described as "Often" which further implies that the research respondents are frequently practicing the 21st century skills in information, media and technology in their teaching.

Life and career

Table 3
21st Century Skills Practiced by the Teachers in terms Life and Career

Life and Career	WM	Description
1. Build harmonious relationship with the learners by knowing when to talk and when to listen.	4.9	Always
2. Give value and respect to other opinions, ideas and beliefs.	4.8	Always
3. Ensure that the learners' differences are accepted and the needs of individual learners are addressed to the best extent possible regardless of other backgrounds.	4.7	Always
4. Respect cultural differences and work effectively with people from a range of social and cultural backgrounds.	4.8	Always
5. Participate in trainings that promote peace and understanding of cultural diversity.	4.4	Always
6. Manage and document conflicts that arise in the classroom.	4.5	Always
7. Design learning activities that reflect the different backgrounds and needs of the students.	4.3	Always
8. Treat each learner as an individual deserving of respect and not as a representative of a group.	4.7	Always
9. Practice cooperative learning by encouraging cooperative learning tasks and discouraging negative competition among learners.	4.6	Always
10. Select materials that reflect the different backgrounds and needs of the learners.	4.3	Always
11. Able to adapt any changes that may occur in the learning environment.	4.5	Always
12. Keep things balanced not only tasks and responsibilities but also the diverse views and belief to reach workable solutions, particularly in a multicultural environment.	4.6	Always
13. Negotiate to teach a peaceable resolution or compromise acceptable to everyone.	4.2	Often
14. Utilize time and manage workload efficiently.	4.5	Always
15. Go beyond basic mastery of the skills and curriculum to explore and expand one's own learning and opportunities to gain expertise.	4.4	Always
16. Establish commitment to learning as a lifelong process.	4.7	Always
17. Reflect critically on past experiences in order to inform future progress.	4.6	Always
18. Collaborate and cooperate effectively with team.	4.6	Always
19. Delegate some task that my learners that can easily do in their own.	4.5	Always
20. Has the innate ability to inspire, energize and encourage the learners and everyone.	4.5	Always
AWM	4.6	Always

As reflected in table 3, nineteen of the twenty indicators of the 21st century practiced by teachers in terms of life and career described research respondents as "Always" while "Negotiate to teach a peaceable resolution or compromise acceptable to everyone." got a weighted mean of 4.2 as described to have "Often"

practiced life and career 21st century skills. It implies that research respondents had practiced life and career in their teaching skills and build harmonious relationship with the learners by knowing when to talk and when to listen. It has an overall weighted mean of 4.6 described as "Always". it further implies that

research respondents had establish commitment and respect learning as a lifelong process. They treat their learner as an individual deserving of respect and not as a representative of a group.

Knowledge and Skills of Teachers in Inclusive Education

Table 4
Knowledge and Skills of Teachers in Inclusive Education

Statements	WM	Description
1. My educational background has prepared me to effectively teach students with cognitive delays and deficits in daily living skills.	4.3	Strongly Agree
2. I need more training in order to appropriately teach students with a learner with special need for learning.	4.6	Strongly Agree
3. I am encouraged by my administrators to attend conference/workshops on teaching students with a learner with special needs in my classroom	4.0	Agree
4. My colleagues are willing to help me with issues which may arise when I have students with a learner with special needs in my classroom.	4.3	Strongly Agree
5. I feel comfortable in working collaboratively with special education teachers when students with a learner with special needs are in my classroom.	4.3	Strongly Agree
6. I welcome collaborative teaching when I have a student with a learner with special needs in my classroom.	4.4	Strongly Agree
7. Students who are two (2) or more years below grade level should be in special education classes.	3.6	Agree
8. Students who are diagnosed as autistic need to be in special education classrooms.	3.6	Agree
9. All efforts should be made to educate students who have a learners with special needs in the regular education classroom.	4.3	Strongly Agree
10. Students who are diagnosed a mentally retarded should be in special education classes.	3.9	Agree
11. Students ho are verbally aggressive towards others can be maintained in regular education classrooms.	3.0	Neutral
12. Collaborative teaching of children with special needs can be effective particularly when students with an IEP are placed in a regular classroom.	3.6	Agree
13. Special education teachers should teach learners with a special needs.	4.4	Strongly Agree
14. I can approach my administrators with concerns hold regarding teaching students who have special needs.	4.2	Agree
15. I feel supported by my administrators when faced with challenges presented by the students with behavioral difficulties in my classroom.	4.0	Agree
16. My district provides me with sufficient out of district training opportunities in order for me to appropriately teach students with disability.	3.5	Agree
17. My educational background has prepared me to teach students with special needs.	4.1	Agree
18. My educational background has prepared ne to teach students with special needs.	3.8	Agree

19. I am provided with sufficient in-service training through my school district which allows me the ability to teach students with a learner with special needs	3.4	Neutral
20. My administrators provide me with sufficient support when I have students with a learners with special needs in my classroom.	3.8	Agree
21. I am provided with enough time in order to attend conferences/workshops on teaching students with special needs.	3.4	Neutral
22. I can approach my colleagues for assistance when needed if I have students with special needs in my classroom.	3.7	Agree
23. Regular education teachers should not be responsible for teaching children with special needs.	3.3	Neutral
24. I like being the only teacher in the classroom,	3.2	Neutral
25. Students who are physically aggressive towards others can be maintained in regular education classrooms.	3.8	Agree
26. All students who have a learners with special needs for any reason need to receive their education in a special education classroom.	3.8	Agree
27. Students who display speech and language difficulties should be in special education classes.	3.8	Agree
28. I should only be responsible for teaching students who are not identified as having special needs.	3.1	Neutral
29. My colleagues are approachable when I ask for their advice when I teach students with special needs.	3.7	Agree
30. Both regular education teachers and special education teachers should teach students with a learners with special needs.	3.6	Agree
31. I am provided with sufficient materials in order to be able to make appropriate accommodations for students with special needs.	3.5	Agree
32. My educational background has prepared me to effectively teach students who are 1 year below level.	3.8	Agree
33. My educational background has prepared me to effectively teach students with speech impairments.	3.6	Agree
34. I need more training in order to appropriately teach learners with special needs for behavioral problems.	4.4	Strongly Agree
35. I feel supported by my administrators when faced with challenges presented by the students with learning difficulties in my classroom.	4.2	Agree
36. I am provided with monetary support in order to attend conferences/workshops on teaching students with special needs.	3.7	Agree
37. I feel comfortable in approaching my colleagues for help when I teach students with special needs.	3.7	Agree
38. Students who are one (1) year below grade level should be in special education classes.	3.3	Neutral
39. Students who are identified as depressed but do not display over disruptive behavior should be in regular education classes.	3.7	Agree
40. Special education teachers might lose their jobs if I teach children with special education.	2.5	Disagree
AWM	3.8	Agree

As shown in Table 4, knowledge and skills of teachers in inclusive education. Out of forty indicators, eight (8) indicators revealed to have answered "Strongly Agree" while twenty four (24) indicator out of forty exposed to have answered "Agree". Seven (7) out of forty exposed neutrality in their knowledge and skills in inclusive education and further one (1) out of forty indicators "Special education teachers might lose their jobs if I teach children with special education." revealed that research respondents "Disagree". It implies that strong indication of the knowledge and skills of teachers in inclusive education had already been performed and agreed in both regular education teachers and special education teachers should teach students with learners with special needs. In summing

up of knowledge and skills of teachers in inclusive education, it has an over weighted mean of 3.8 described as "Agree" which moreover implies that, research respondents have gain knowledge and skills in teaching inclusive education. Further implies that, with commitment and support of the administration of the school and with knowledge and skills of teachers regarding inclusive education surely students with special needs or even regular students will be able to do their task in the inclusive education classroom.

Knowledge and Skills of Students in Inclusive Education

Table 5
Knowledge and Skills of Students in Inclusive Education

Statements	WM	Description
1. By adjusting their classroom to facilitate a stimulating learning environment.	4.6	Strongly Agree
2. By adjusting their teaching to facilitate a creative learning environment.	4.4	Strongly Agree
3. By acknowledging the different needs of all learners irrespective to their age.	4.4	Strongly Agree
4. By acknowledging the different needs of all children irrespective of their language.	4.5	Strongly Agree
5. By acknowledging the different needs of all learners irrespective of their disability.	4.2	Agree
6. By collaborating with professional service providers.	4.5	Strongly Agree
7. By involving parents in the decision making process concerning how to handle their children.	4.5	Strongly Agree
8. By recommending that the learner be transferred to a special school.	3.5	Agree
9. The intellectual abilities of a learner with a special educational needs differ from those of a normal child.	3.9	Agree
10. A learner with a special educational need experiences difficult in adapting to his/her social environment.	3.9	Agree
11. A learner with special educational need gives appropriate answers when questions are asked.	3.8	Agree
12. The attentiveness of a learner with special educational need is weaker than that of a normal child.	3.5	Agree
13. A learner with special educational need has a poor reading abilities.	3.4	Neutral
14. A learner with special educational need can function independently within the classroom.	3.3	Neutral
15. A learner with special educational need needs additional assistance from the teacher.	4.2	Agree
16. The academic progress of a learner with special educational need is weaker compared to a normal child of the same age.	3.6	Agree
AWM	4.0	Agree

As reflected in table 5, knowledge and skills of student in inclusive education. Six (6) out of sixteen indicators revealed to have answered "Strongly Agree" by the research respondents. Eight (8) indicators were claimed to have answered "Agree" by the research respondents and two (2) indicators revealed to have neutrality answered by the research respondents. This implies that, students' respondents have knowledge and skills in inclusive education. In summing up of knowledge and skills of students in inclusive education. It has an overall weighted mean of 4.0 described as "Agree". This further implies that, students respondents can adjust and acknowledge the

different needs of classmates inside the classroom. Collaboration and cooperation of stakeholders and parents surely help in an efficient delivery of inclusive education in the normal classroom stream.

Relationship of Variables

This section presents the significant relationship between 21st century skills practiced by teachers and student's knowledge and skills in inclusive education. This is presented in Table 6.

Table 6
Significant Relationship between 21st Century Skills Practiced by Teachers Knowledge and Skills in Inclusive Education

Variable	r-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Learning and innovation	.294	.097	Ho Accepted
Information, media and technology	.451**	.008	Ho Rejected
Life and Career	.588**	.000	Ho Rejected

**Correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed)

Table 6 shows the significant relationship between the 21st century skills practiced by teachers' knowledge and skills in inclusive education.

The teacher's 21st century skills in terms of learning and innovation obtained correlation r-value of .294 with sig. (2-tailed) of .097 which means that the hypothesis was accepted. It implies that the learning and innovation skills are not directly related or affected by teachers' knowledge and skills in inclusive education.

However, information, media and technology skills attained r- value of .451** and .008 significant at the .01 level (2-tailed). Moreover, life and career skills obtained r-value of .588** and sig. (2-tailed) at .000 which is significant at .01 level. The results implies that the hypotheses were rejected. This means that the teacher's 21st century skills in terms of information, media and technology and life and career are significantly related to the student's knowledge and skills in inclusive education.

Table 7
Significant Relationship between 21st Century Skills Practiced by Students and their Knowledge and Skills in Inclusive Education

Variable	r-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Learning and innovation	.447**	.009	Ho Rejected
Information, media and technology	.595**	.000	Ho Rejected
Life and Career	.300	.090	Ho Accepted

**Correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed)

Table 7 shows the significant relationship between the 21st century skills practiced by students and their knowledge and skills in inclusive education.

The teacher's 21st century skills in terms of learning and innovation obtained correlation r-value of .447** with sig. (2-tailed) of .009 which means that the hypothesis was rejected. Moreover, information, media and technology obtained correlation r-value of .595** with sig. (2-tailed) of .000 which significant at .01 level. The results may imply that the hypotheses were rejected. Further implies that the 21st century skills of students in terms of learning and innovation and information, media and technology are significantly related to students knowledge and skills in inclusive education.

However, life and career skills of teachers obtained correlation r-value of .300 with sig. (2-tailed) of .090 which means that the hypothesis was accepted. It further implies that the life and career skills of students are not directly or affected their knowledge and skills in inclusive education.

Feedbacks in Inclusive Education

Learners with Special Educational Needs

Different learning styles were used by teachers in an inclusive education classroom. Teachers helps students with special needs to be able to follow and allow them to work normally and were accepted to the whole class. Students are taking cared up by teachers whether they need special attention or not.

Understanding, patients and even adjustment of teachers is very important, so that students with special needs will adapt and be respected by other normal students. Teachers be inclined to embrace everything to be able to teach normally to learners with special needs by using different learning styles and modalities inside an inclusive classroom.

Inclusive Education/Learning

Inclusive education is a great system to help children with their educational needs. It welcomes everyone and accepted to the program either by appearance, sexual preferences, special needs, cultural differences, economic status, gender, and race. Teachers help students develop their skills, promotes personal academic and professional development. Further, through inclusive education students are able to open up and show whatever their hidden talents and by teachers encouragement they will start developing their self-confidence particularly the learners with special needs. Furthermore, Inclusive education is for all kinds of learners with different learning styles and preferences. Through teachers and school students with special needs will be able to reach their full potentials and can work harmoniously to the normal classroom stream with regular students with no discrimination will everyone acquire quality and standard education.

Equality in Education

Based on the learning from their teachers, inclusive education pointed out equality and fairness

in a well motivated learning environment where everyone can learn equally and learners with special needs will be treated with utmost sincerity by teachers. No rich and poor status, smart or dumb, black or white. Equality has been practice where everyone is accepted. Quality education were emphasize and distributed equally to all students. It allows everyone to adapt to the needs and concerns of the learners with respect according to his/her personality.

Feelings and Emotions in Inclusive Education

Educational Satisfaction

A feeling of satisfaction because every student needs to be treated equally with no discrimination, comparison and judgment. A feeling happiness and understanding of having many friends to work with and meeting diversified students are great in one classroom setting. In my personal opinion I am really thankful that I belong in an inclusive education classroom because of this I was able to do everything. Inclusive education is pleasing and grateful to students with different backgrounds and have different experiences in life. Normal students will adjust to learners with special needs and not to be envy for they have full teachers attention. A scene like cooperation were done inside the inclusive classroom because normal students will assist their classmates with difficulties in their studies. Further, school to have inclusive education will continue to operate and continue to understand that learners with special needs for they will be able to help them in their plight towards attaining educational ladders.

Great Solution

Inclusive education is the solution to learners with special needs. Isolation is not the way to teach learners with special needs. They will be included to the regular class for them to experience the real classroom scenario where teaching and learning is fun and students are free to ask and talk in front of their classmates and teacher. Learners with special needs are welcome and can specks their true feelings and helping them to have self confidence and to be a competitive learners. Introvert learners have the time to express their feelings and sentiments in an inclusive

class. Lastly, learners with special needs are always welcome to the inclusive classroom.

Acceptance

Learners with special needs were fully accepted and acknowledge in an inclusive classroom. Acceptance will make them real learners boosting with self-confidence and not rejected. Normal learners are open-minded about the difficulties of the classmates with special needs accept their opinions and ideas. Through acceptance, learners with difficulties will be able to share, distribute his ideas freely compared to those isolated learners. Accepted by friends and classmates can be of great help to increase their self-esteem and cope up with their problems and troubles in school.

Necessary Skills in Inclusive Education

Communication Skills

Teacher should have possesses communication skills to convey properly and correctly the needed teaching and learning to his learners. With appropriate use of language in communication learners will be able to comprehend and grasp the essence and the delivery of instruction. Taking into consideration the learners with special needs. Effective communication skills of the teacher is an essentials tool to make learners understand the topic discuss particularly the learners with special needs. Having said that, using appropriate communication skills of the teachers may lead to an advantage of the learners in their learning and can boost their self confidence. Inclusive education classroom needs 21st first teachers and skills needed for accurate delivery of the pedagogy. Analytical Teaching Skills

Problem solving and analytical skills of teachers may lead to an harmonious teaching and learning of the 21st century inclusive education classroom. Teachers in the 21st century needs skills in critical and logical for him so solve classroom problems. It is important to have this skills because teachers are handling not only normal learners but also learners with special needs. This skills also necessary for teachers to increase and develop positivity of the

learners with special needs to enhance and reveal their hidden talents and be productive. Further, teachers will be able to expose their learners to positive outlook in life to avoid problems of bullying in the future.

Social and Understanding Skills

Teachers understanding more about the students difficulties and problems is his utmost responsibility. Interpersonal and intrapersonal skills are just normal to students of inclusive education class. Teachers should have excellent in social learning skills to be able to appreciate each learners different ways of learning.

Teachers should have extra sense of humor and effort for his gigantic task in handling inclusive education class. Extending patients and unending love with passion by the teachers are immensely needed in an inclusive education classroom. Lastly, teachers with social and understanding skills will have a clear print of learning in the minds of his learners both normal and learners with special needs.

Needs of Learners in Inclusive Education

Encouragement

Teachers caters the needs of the learners by knowing themselves better and encouraged every learners to make sure that they stay confident and happy of themselves inside the inclusive education class. Positivity in times of problems and bad situations, interact with passion and commitment in teaching the learners. Teachers encourage their learners to do their best and to listen to the class attentively and never give up. Looking into the bright light of the story and not on the dark side of it. Through encouragement and support of the teachers, learners of an inclusive education class will be able to adapt the real inclusive classroom situation with a lot of opportunity and learners are just enjoying the class with utmost confidence.

Respect

Respect is immensely important inside inclusive classroom. Mutual respect between teachers and students can mean a lot to teaching and learning in an

inclusive classroom. Teachers will accept learners imperfections, agreed and recognize their potentials will enhance the self-assurance of the learners. There are incidents of bullying happens in a class, bullying with learners to learners and teachers to learners. With respect both learners and teachers, admiration and appreciation will be seen in an inclusive classroom. If teachers are respecting the learners give their full support, listen to their problems and cater their needs there is a huge possibility of a quality learning of not only the "normal learners" but also the learners with special needs.

Adjustment

Learners with special needs are sensitive. Teachers should be aware of his learners strengths and weaknesses and teachers adjustment mean a lot in an inclusive classroom. Inclusive education is about a relationship between a student and teacher. Fine-tune the scenario of a normal classroom. Inclusive education classroom provides learners to attain their full potentials and develop their abilities that are very useful in their future undertakings. Adjustment between learners and teachers is essential since learners are diverse with different experiences, economic status, family background and etc. Normal learners will adjust to learners with special needs so that bullying will not happen. Teachers will adjust to his learners, put himself to the shoes of his learners especially the learners with special needs. Doing adjustment both learners and teachers makes the inclusive classroom more fruitful and learning is fun. "I adjust to the needs of all the learners in my class by trying to help them in the topics that they do not fully understand as well as helping them to finish academic tasks that they have difficulty to finish".

Specific trainings in Inclusive Education

Leadership Training

Leadership training is important to help others and lead others to do good things. This training will increase the teachers capability to manage and teach learners with special needs and regular learners. Leadership training will lead others to success. "Leadership training, learn to be a good leader in your

team, learn to understand, and learn to adjust in your surroundings. Leadership training to have a respect to other people because we are just also a human to avoid racism, to be a responsible person. I'd like to try the leadership training to see and understand how to be a successful leader." Leadership training enhance teachers to become responsible leader, and lead his/her members for the good of every member of his/her class. Teachers needs to have this training to control and manage inclusive education classroom where diversity and multiplicity are obvious not only in regular learners but also in learners with special needs. Teachers' patience is essential and paramount in dealing his class everyday.

Social Responsibility Training

A training where we can learn how to be independent, how to survive harsh circumstances, and how to not discriminate other people. The training that I would like to learn is how to service how to learn, live and protect yourself. I would want to train to be a doctor because it is good to become one cause you handle kids emotions or adults and help someone imagine someone got hurt then you can go to him/her to help. I would like to participate being in a social training and to be able to learn how to be content and less insecurity. Yes there is, it is a training where you can improve your communication skills so that you can accurately explain what they need. Training for what are the things you must learn and understand in inclusive education. For what is the purpose of inclusive education and what are the needs on this education.

Team Building Training

"Yes. In education, I can see that many of the problems of students are insecurity, self-doubt and self-inferiority and more. It all affects the student's personality. All of these negative vibes a are affecting the attitude of the students. Therefore we need to have training in team building, to have teamwork and to always be positive and ignore negative vibes and even let the learners adjust to what he/she is comfortable and avoid false trash comments." "It would be honesty and to never give up and teamwork and to be responsible. A training where students are required to

cooperate in a team-building game with people with disabilities and special needs. They must learn to work well with people despite of disabilities in order to overcome the obstacles of success.

Comments in Inclusive Education

Education for All

Teachers believed that inclusive education can help learners with special develop their sense of responsibility and become useful in their future activities. Teachers also believe that through inclusive education learners will be accepted and not being judge of his or her difficulties in learning. A feeling of self independent is also the mean purpose of inclusive education. Learners will learn to become more respectful of their classmates and teachers. A classroom where a lot of learners experiences and diversified learning. Learners with special needs are welcomed and accepted in an inclusive education classroom where values and good moral are being shared between learners and teachers. "I like the inclusive education compare to non-inclusive education because non-inclusive education is not letting person with special needs and ordinary people be in one class and to friends compare to inclusive education it adjust on you." Moreover, inclusive education is very important were equality, respect, adjustment, hope, encouragement, and acceptance are seen in an inclusive education classroom.

2. Conclusion

As gleaned from the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn.

21st Century Skills Practiced by the Teachers on learning innovation were often practiced while information, media and technology and life and career were always practiced by teachers respectively.

Regarding, knowledge and skills of teachers had already been performed and agreed in both regular education teachers and special education teachers. Students have knowledge and skills in inclusive education. Students' respondents can adjust and

acknowledge the different needs of classmates inside the classroom.

Moreover, learning and innovation and information, media and technology knowledge and skills practiced by teachers are significantly related. However, life and career skills are not directly affected by knowledge and skills practiced by teachers.

Further, learning and innovation skills are not directly related or affected by student's knowledge and skills in inclusive education while information, media and technology and life and career are significantly related to student's knowledge and skills.

Lastly, understanding in inclusive education anchors in learners with special needs, inclusive education and learning, and equality in education. There's a feeling happiness, satisfaction, and understanding felt by teachers inside inclusive classroom. Teachers possesses communication skills, analytical teaching skills and social and understanding skills in handling inclusive class. Leadership training, social responsibility training, and team building are trainings helps improve and increase teachers motivation and commitment in teaching inclusive education class were the aim is to give quality education for all.

Recommendations

Based on the issues and implications of the results, the following recommendations are forwarded.

1. Trainings, seminars and conferences in teaching inclusive education could enhance and increase teachers' motivation and commitment in teaching inclusive education class.
2. Learners with special needs should be included in a regular classroom where his educational needs can fully be given attention by teachers and his potentialities can function independently.
3. 21st century skills should be given importance to be delivered not only to regular learners but also to learners with special needs.
4. Acceptance, encouragement, respect and adjustment of teachers to the learners with special

needs should be given priority to attain the goals of education which is education for all.

5. Intensive and focus trainings in leadership, social responsibility and capacity building should be given emphasis by teachers to recognize the different needs of learners with special needs and regular learners.

6. A follow-up research focusing on the wider scope should be conducted to determine the effectiveness of the 21st century knowledge and skills practice by teachers and students herein recommended for implementation.

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